

ISic1136

I.Sicily inscription 1136

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 138

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. []
2. [έ]π,ι, ,τò áλειπ[τήριονέκτοϋ]
3. [ί]δίου ποιήσ,α,ν,τ,α
4. [κ]αί τās διώρυγας κ,α,ι, ,τ[άν]
5. [σ]τρῶσιν τās πλατείας τὰ[ν]
6. [ά]πò τοϋ λίθου τοϋ
7. θηγανείτα άπό τās
8. [π]ύλας τās παρά
9. θάλασσαν έκ τοϋ ιδίο[υ]
10. [π]ο,ιήσαντα (vac.undefined) εύνοίας
11. [ένεκα]

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492749

EDR 135919

EDCS 39102293

PHI 140621

Bibliography

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